

Virtualized GPU Offloading for AI Inference: Enabling Deep Learning Frameworks on GPU-less Devices

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Abstract—The deployment of Deep Learning (DL) inference on resource-constrained endpoint devices is often hampered by the absence of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) creates performance bottlenecks for real-time applications. This paper presents a virtualized GPU offloading framework that enables devices to execute demanding AI workloads by transparently leveraging a remote, high-performance GPU. Our system is based on an enhanced version of the GVirtuS framework, updated to support CUDA 12.6 and integrated with DL libraries, including PyTorch, Caffe, and OpenCV DNN. We validated our framework on representative AI tasks, including human pose estimation and image classification. The experimental results demonstrate substantial performance gains, achieving up to a 17.8x speedup over CPU-only execution while maintaining ease of deployment. This work confirms that transparent remote GPU acceleration is a practical and effective solution for unlocking high-performance AI capabilities on the vast ecosystem of GPU-less devices.

Index Terms—GPU virtualization, HPC, Deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The remarkable success of Deep Learning (DL) has catalyzed the deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) across a myriad of domains, from autonomous driving [1] and medical image analysis [2] to real-time video analytics [3] and intelligent surveillance [4]. Central to this proliferation are deep neural networks (DNNs), which, while delivering unprecedented accuracy, demand substantial computational resources, particularly GPU acceleration, for efficient inference [5]. However, a significant paradigm conflict emerges in practical deployment scenarios. A vast ecosystem of endpoint devices, such as edge computing nodes, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, and legacy industrial PCs, is computationally constrained and often lacks powerful GPU hardware. Executing modern DNN models on

these devices using Central Processing Units (CPUs) alone often results in prohibitively high latency and low throughput, rendering them unsuitable for real-time applications [6]. Conversely, equipping every endpoint with a high-performance GPU is economically infeasible and energetically inefficient.

This challenge has spurred research into computational offloading, where intensive tasks are delegated to powerful remote servers. Existing solutions often involve: using cloud-based inference APIs (e.g., AWS SageMaker, Azure ML), which may introduce significant network latency and raise data privacy concerns; or relying on framework-specific inference engines (e.g., TensorRT, OpenVINO) to optimize execution on supported hardware, which typically requires model conversion and explicit code modifications. These approaches lack generality, binding applications to a specific service or framework and necessitating non-trivial changes to the existing codebase.

A more elegant solution lies in GPU virtualization, which aims to decouple physical GPU resources from the local hardware environment. Prior systems, such as rCUDA [7], have demonstrated the feasibility of remote CUDA execution. Their primary focus, however, has often been on enabling high-performance computing (HPC) workloads in cluster environments, rather than optimizing the end-to-end latency of interactive, DL inference tasks on lightweight edge devices. Moreover, rCUDA is not open-source, limiting its accessibility and adaptability for broader research and deployment.

In this paper, based on GVirtuS [8], [9], we employ a transparent GPU virtualization framework on CUDA 12.6 explicitly designed to enable efficient DL inference in resource-constrained environments. Our system allows unmodified applications built on widely used DL frameworks—such as Caffe, PyTorch, and OpenCV DNN—to seamlessly offload CUDA calls to a remote server equipped with a GPU. While GVirtuS already offers a general-purpose mechanism for in-

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TABLE I
SUPPORTED CUDA LIBRARY FUNCTIONS IN THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK.

Library	Nr. of supported functions
cuDNN	388
cuBLAS	432
cuSOLVER	8
cuFFT	80
cuSPARSE	202
cuRAND	30

intercepting and forwarding CUDA API calls at the dynamic library level, our contribution lies in adapting and extending this approach to support interactive inference workloads better. In addition, we have updated GVirtuS support to CUDA 12.6, ensuring compatibility with modern GPU features and enhancing its applicability in current DL environments. Specifically, we integrate GPU virtualization with high-level DL libraries, providing complete transparency to the application: no modifications to the source code or the pre-trained models are required. The remote server executes these calls and returns the results, effectively granting the client device virtualized access to a GPU. Our main contributions in this work can be recapped as follows:

- We update GVirtuS to support the widely used deep learning frameworks (e.g., OpenCV DNN, PyTorch, Caffe) and the latest version of CUDA that they support, which at the time of writing of this paper is CUDA 12.6^{1,2,3}, enabling applications to transparently offload inference workloads to remote GPUs without requiring source code modifications. The new release has been upgraded and extended significantly, and it currently provides comprehensive coverage of the major CUDA libraries and the functions used by DL frameworks, as shown in Table I.
- We evaluate the proposed framework on representative DNN applications (OpenPose [10] for key point detection, SqueezeNet [11], ResNet [12], and VGG [13] for classification). Results demonstrate that our approach achieves significant speedup compared to CPU while maintaining compatibility, transparency, and ease of deployment across different frameworks. Although it is generally slower than native GPU execution, on certain tasks our framework achieves performance that is comparable to native GPUs.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related work in GPU virtualization and DNN deployment. Section III details the design of our system, describing implementation challenges and corresponding solutions. Section IV presents our experimental setup and results. Section V concludes the paper and outlines avenues for future work.

¹<https://github.com/pytorch/pytorch/releases>

²<https://github.com/opencv/opencv/wiki/OpenCV-Change-Logs#version4120>

³<https://caffe.berkeleyvision.org/>

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we review prior works in GPU virtualization, remote DL inference, and integration with the DL frameworks, which are relevant to our study.

GPU Virtualization and Remote CUDA Execution. Early efforts in GPU virtualization aimed to decouple GPU resources from local hardware constraints. Systems such as rCUDA [7] and GVirtuS [8], [9] demonstrated that CUDA applications can be executed remotely by intercepting API calls and forwarding them to GPU-equipped servers. These systems primarily targeted HPC environments, where the goal was to provide efficient GPU sharing across nodes in a cluster. While effective in batch-oriented workloads, they were not explicitly designed for latency-sensitive, interactive inference tasks. Other approaches, such as virtualization-based GPU passthrough [14] or containerized GPU sharing [15], provide near-native performance but require direct access to physical GPUs, making them unsuitable for lightweight edge devices.

Deep Learning Deployment on Resource-Constrained Devices. Recent research has explored running DNNs on resource-limited platforms such as mobile and IoT devices. Solutions range from model compression [16] and quantization [17] to hardware acceleration on specialized NPU [18]. While these methods reduce local computational costs, they often involve significant engineering effort, reduced model accuracy, or hardware dependency. Remote inference services (e.g., TensorFlow Serving, NVIDIA Triton Inference Server) provide cloud-based acceleration but usually require applications to be adapted to specific frameworks, limiting transparency and ease of integration.

Integration with Deep Learning Frameworks. In practice, developers often rely on high-level DL libraries such as OpenCV DNN [19], PyTorch [20], or Caffe [21], which provide unified interfaces for deploying a wide range of neural network models. Some efforts have adapted specific frameworks to GPU virtualization. For example, AVEC [22], [23] demonstrates GPU offloading on the Caffe DL library with OpenPose, but it is not open source. In contrast, rInfer [24] adopts a Remote Procedure Call (RPC) model, where inference requests are transparently executed on remote GPUs using PyTorch and TensorRT. Our work also follows the offloading paradigm, but extends GVirtuS to support multiple mainstream DL frameworks, enabling transparent and efficient GPU offloading acceleration for DL inference on resource-constrained devices.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The goal of our system is to enable transparent remote GPU acceleration for DL inference on devices without local GPUs. As shown in Fig. 1, the system consists of two main components: the client, which runs the unmodified application using popular DL frameworks, and the server, which hosts a GPU to execute CUDA calls. Communication between client and server is handled over a standard TCP/IP network. Our design maintains full compatibility with pre-trained models

Fig. 1. GPU Virtualization Architecture.

such as PTH and ONNX, without necessitating any changes to source code or model parameters.

Client-Side Architecture. On the client side, we leverage GVirtuS [8], [9], [25] to intercept CUDA API calls generated by the DL frameworks. In this work, we have updated GVirtuS to provide full support for CUDA 12.6. The interception is implemented via a dynamic library hook, which captures runtime calls such as memory allocation, data transfer, and kernel execution. Captured calls are then serialized into messages containing function identifiers, arguments, and data payloads. These messages are sent over the TCP/IP network to the remote server. The client remains unaware of the remote execution; from the application’s perspective, CUDA operations appear to execute locally.

Server-Side Architecture. The server receives serialized CUDA requests from clients and invokes the corresponding CUDA runtime or driver functions on the GPU. Once the execution completes, results, including device pointers, computation outputs, or status codes, are serialized and returned to the client. The server can handle multiple concurrent client requests, enabling resource sharing across applications and devices. By separating computation from the client, our system allows lightweight devices to benefit from high-performance GPU acceleration without hardware modifications.

Communication Protocol. Communication between client and server is implemented over TCP/IP. Each CUDA API call is serialized into a structured message that includes the function ID, arguments, and data payloads. Responses are similarly serialized to ensure correct mapping to the original request.

A. Integration with Deep Learning Frameworks

To support a wide range of AI models, our system is designed to be compatible with multiple DL frameworks, including Caffe, OpenCV DNN, and PyTorch. Applications can invoke standard framework APIs (e.g., `cv::dnn::Net::forward()` in OpenCV or `torch::jit::forward()` in PyTorch) without modification, while the dynamic library transparently intercepts and forwards CUDA calls to the remote server. This integration ensures that developers can leverage existing

TABLE II
HARDWARE USED IN THE ENVIRONMENT.

	Client	Server
GPU	\	NVIDIA RTX A5000
GPU Memory	\	24 GB GDDR6
CPU Memory	512 GB	512 GB
CPU Cores	64	24
CUDA Toolkit	12.6	12.6
cuDNN	9.5.1	9.5.1

pipelines across different frameworks while benefiting from remote GPU acceleration in a completely transparent manner.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Experimental Setup

We evaluated our system on a client-server setup. The server was equipped with an NVIDIA RTX A5000 GPU, 512 GB of RAM, and ran Ubuntu 22.04 with CUDA 12.6. The client was a CPU-only machine with an AMD EPYC 7702P 64-Core Processor and 512 GB of RAM, connected to the server over a 20 Gbit/s Ethernet link (bonded interface). The hardware used in the environment is shown in Tab. II. For comparison, we executed inference workloads in three configurations:

- **Local (CPU-only):** DL frameworks executed solely on the client CPU.
- **With GVirtuS:** Frameworks run on the client while transparently offloading CUDA calls to a remote server via GVirtuS.
- **Native GPU:** Frameworks executed directly on the server with local GPU access.

We conducted experiments on two representative tasks: human pose estimation and image classification. For the human pose estimation task, we randomly selected 100 unique images labeled as “person” from the COCO 2014 dataset [26] and processed them using the OpenPose implementation based on Caffe. For the classification task, we utilized pre-trained models from the ONNX Model Zoo [27] and TorchVision [28]. From the ImageNet test set [29], we randomly sampled one image per class, resulting in a total of 1000 images for evaluation.

B. Performance of Caffe with GVirtuS

OpenPose was developed for real-time human pose estimation. As illustrated in Fig. 2, it detects body keypoints and overlays pose annotations directly on input images. Since this task is highly time-sensitive, efficient processing is essential for handling live video streams or large-scale image datasets. To address these computational demands, we evaluate the performance of OpenPose under different execution environments.

As shown in Fig. 3, leveraging GVirtuS significantly accelerates processing compared to CPU-only execution, reducing the total time for 100 images from 910.87s to 51.23s, corresponding to an approximate 17.8× speedup. Although GVirtuS remains slower than a native GPU (51.23s vs. 16.33s), it still

Fig. 2. Example of human pose estimation.

Fig. 3. Per-image execution time of **OpenPose**. The total time for 100 images is 910.87 s, 51.23 s, 16.33 s, for the CPU, GVirtuS, and native GPU case, respectively.

Fig. 4. Execution time comparison of the classification task using **OpenCV**. GVirtuS exhibits lower performance than CPU inference at a batch size of 1, but as the batch size increases, its execution efficiency progressively approaches that of the native GPU.

achieves a considerable portion of GPU performance while providing the flexibility and convenience of virtualization.

In addition, Fig. 3 illustrates the per-image inference time of OpenPose. It can be observed that the first image requires an extra initialization period of 1-2 s across all environments. After this phase, each subsequent image is processed at a relatively stable rate. With GVirtuS, the average processing time per image is around 0.5 s, compared to 9 s on the CPU and 0.15 s on the native GPU.

C. Performance of OpenCV DNN and Pytorch with GVirtuS

We evaluated the acceleration performance of GVirtuS for a series of classification tasks across six models of varying scales: SqueezeNet, ResNet18, ResNet50, ResNet152, VGG16, and VGG19. As shown in Fig. 4 and 5, when the batch size is set to 1, the performance achieved with GVirtuS is generally inferior to that of using the CPU on the client side, particularly for smaller-scale models. For such models, the computational demand at small batch sizes is relatively low, which limits the ability to leverage GPU acceleration

effectively. Consequently, the majority of the time overhead is dominated by communication costs associated with CUDA calls. This effect is mitigated when the model size or batch size increases. In the former case, the computational demand grows, while in the latter, a larger batch size not only makes better use of the GPU’s tensor computation capabilities but also reduces the total number of CUDA calls required for the same test set, thereby further lowering communication overhead. Notably, as the batch size grows, the performance gap between GVirtuS and the native GPU implementation narrows. For example, in the case of VGG16 and VGG19, when the batch size increases to 100 or 200, GVirtuS achieves execution times that are very close to native GPU performance.

In addition, we observed that OpenCV outperforms PyTorch in tasks with small batch sizes, whereas PyTorch is better suited for large-scale batch processing. As shown in Tab. III and IV, we analyzed the CUDA call patterns of both frameworks when executing a single image and found that PyTorch invokes substantially more CUDA functions than OpenCV. Among these, a large proportion is associated

Fig. 5. Execution time comparison of classification task using **PyTorch**. The results show a similar trend to the OpenCV implementation, with GVirtuS achieving performance increasingly close to the native GPU as the batch size grows.

TABLE III

MODEL PARAMETERS AND AMOUNT OF DATA TRANSFER USING **OPENCV** WITH IMAGENET. THE NUMBER OF CUDA FUNCTION CALLS SHOWN IS PER IMAGE. NOTE THAT THE PREDICTIVE ACCURACY REMAINS THE SAME ACROSS CPU, GPU, AND GVIRTUS EXECUTIONS.

	SqueezeNet1.1	ResNet18	VGG16
model size (MB)	4.73	44.65	527.97
Client-Server (MB)	15.75	55.63	539.10
Server-Client (MB)	0.23	0.23	0.22
# CUDA functions	2495	2353	2011

TABLE IV

MODEL PARAMETERS AND SIZE OF DATA TRANSFER USING **PYTORCH** WITH IMAGENET. THE NUMBER OF CUDA FUNCTION CALLS SHOWN IS PER IMAGE. NOTE THAT THE PREDICTIVE ACCURACY REMAINS THE SAME ACROSS CPU, GPU, AND GVIRTUS EXECUTIONS.

	SqueezeNet1.1	ResNet18	VGG16
model size (MB)	4.73	44.63	527.93
Client-Server (MB)	1766.59	1804.13	2290.52
Server-Client (MB)	5.95	5.94	5.93
# CUDA functions	37 423	36 244	33 537

with registration-related operations (e.g., memory or context registration), which account for most of the observed overhead. This difference can be attributed to the design characteristics of the two frameworks. OpenCV adopts a relatively lightweight execution model that involves fewer GPU context switches and less memory management overhead, making it more efficient for small or short-duration workloads. In contrast, PyTorch implements a more flexible and modular computation graph architecture, which introduces additional CUDA calls related to kernel scheduling and memory management. While these operations increase overhead when batch sizes are small, they allow PyTorch to achieve better GPU utilization and throughput in large-scale or highly parallel workloads. Consequently, OpenCV tends to deliver better performance in latency-sensitive scenarios, whereas PyTorch demonstrates superior efficiency in high-throughput tasks or when processing larger batches.

D. Discussion

Our experimental results confirm the effectiveness of the GVirtuS-based framework for transparent remote GPU acceleration of DL inference on GPU-less edge devices. Compared

to prior work like rInfer [24] and AVEC [22], [23], GVirtuS offers distinct advantages. While rInfer focuses on generic high-performance remote inference, often in batch-processing scenarios, and AVEC primarily targets Caffe as a prototype, GVirtuS provides transparent, dynamic library-level interception across a broader range of mainstream DL frameworks (Caffe, PyTorch, OpenCV DNN) with CUDA 12.6. Our framework is specifically optimized for interactive, latency-sensitive inference tasks, prioritizing real-time responsiveness and ease of deployment on lightweight edge devices without application modification.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented a practical framework for transparent remote GPU acceleration of DL inference workloads on devices without local GPU resources. Building upon GVirtuS, our system allows unmodified applications to offload CUDA calls to a remote GPU server, enabling significant speedup compared to CPU-only execution while maintaining full compatibility with pre-trained AI models. Experimental results on representative models such as OpenPose, VGG and ResNet demonstrate that our approach achieves near-native

GPU performance under typical network conditions, providing a feasible solution for resource-constrained devices and edge computing scenarios.

Despite the promising results, there are several avenues for future work. First, network latency remains a key factor influencing performance; integrating optimizations such as batched CUDA calls, asynchronous execution, or more efficient data serialization could further reduce overhead. Second, extending the framework to support multiple clients concurrently, with intelligent scheduling and load balancing, would improve scalability in multi-device deployments. Finally, exploring integration with other high-level vision frameworks or DL libraries could broaden the applicability of our approach and simplify adoption across diverse application domains.

In conclusion, our work demonstrates that leveraging existing GPU virtualization techniques, when carefully integrated with popular high-level DL frameworks, can provide an effective and practical approach to enabling high-performance DL inference on devices without local GPUs.

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